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Transforming Engineering Education: DESIGN must be the Core

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ABSTRACT

There have been many reviews of engineering education over the last 15 years, yet most engineering curricula remain traditionally focused on the development of technical outcomes, with a small emphasis on design. This paper reviews many of the international reviews, to seek the common themes that need to be addressed. Examples of new curricula are provided. Although the design of new curricula is difficult enough, it is the implementation of change within our existing academic structures that is really the difficult problem to be solved.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: engineering education transformation, engineering curricula, project-based learning, graduate outcomes, accreditation

INTRODUCTION

There have been numerous international reviews calling for changes to engineering education [1-9]. The key recommendations are enlightening and complementary. However, the sense of urgency for change seems curiously absent, despite many such reports over the last 15 years.

This paper first seeks the common recommendations from several international reviews. It then considers the gaps between these recommendations and typical engineering curricula. Primarily, there is a lack of engineering practice in most programs. The paper then considers required graduate outcomes as expressed in accreditation criteria and how these might be reorganised to provide a different emphasis, focusing on design rather than the technical knowledge that supports it. Examples are provided of design-oriented or project-oriented curricula, which are gradually becoming more common in Australia. However, space precludes discussion of these in detail. Nevertheless, the references provide enough information to seek out more information about, and evaluation of, these programs. Finally, the conclusions encourage all engineering educators to rethink their curricula from one based on engineering science to one based on engineering design.

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1 INTERNATIONAL REVIEWS OF ENGINEERING EDUCATION

The US National Academy of Engineering's *Engineer of 2020* report [1] presented a vision for future engineering (my emphasis):

1. ... profound impact of the engineering profession on **sociocultural systems**, ...
2. ... engineers competent to address the **world's complex and changing challenges**.
3. We aspire to engineers in 2020 who will ... **expand their vision of design**
4. ... an engineering profession that will rapidly embrace the potentialities offered by **creativity, invention, and crossdisciplinary fertilization**
5. ... engineers who will assume **leadership positions**
6. ... an engineering profession that will welcome **underrepresented groups** to its ranks
7. ... engineers will continue to be leaders in the movement toward ... **sustainable development**
8. ... engineers are prepared to adapt to changes in global forces and trends and to **ethically assist the world**

Further, the report adds:

*With appropriate thought and consideration, and using new strategic planning tools, we should **reconstitute engineering curricula** and related educational programs to prepare today's engineers for the careers of the future*

Recommendations from the follow-on report, *Educating the Engineer of 2020* [2] are surprisingly non-specific:

1. ... students should be introduced to the "**essence**" of engineering early in their undergraduate careers.
2. Colleges and universities should **endorse research in engineering education** as a valued and rewarded activity for engineering faculty
3. ... institutions must teach students how to be **lifelong learners**.
4. Engineering educators should introduce **interdisciplinary learning** in the undergraduate curriculum
5. ... and explore the use of case studies of engineering **successes and failures** as a learning tool.
6. The engineering education establishment should participate in efforts to **improve public understanding of engineering** and the technology literacy of the public and efforts to improve math, science, and engineering education at the K-12 level.

Perhaps it is not surprising that change has been slow given these non-specific recommendations.

The UK Henley Report [3] highlights the need for three kinds of engineers:

1. The engineer as **specialist** recognises the continued need for engineers who are technical experts of world-class standing.
2. The engineer as **integrator** reflects the need for engineers who can operate and manage across boundaries, be they technical or organisational in a complex business environment.
3. The engineer as **change agent** highlights the critical role engineers must play in providing the creativity, innovation and leadership to shape the industry in an uncertain future.

The engineer as change agent is in tune with recent calls for greater innovation in engineering and many other disciplines, innovation being seen as the underpinning of the future world economy, e.g. [10, 11].

Sheppard, Macatangay et al. [4] concluded that:

1. "... the **tradition of putting theory before practice** and the effort to cover technical knowledge comprehensively allow little opportunity for students to have the kind of deep learning experiences that mirror professional practice and problem solving.
2. The **lab** is a missed opportunity: ... **Design projects** offer opportunities to approximate professional practice, ... However, these opportunities are **typically provided late in the undergraduate program**.
3. Concerns with **ethics and professionalism**, ..., have long had difficulty finding meaningful places within this historical model
4. Further, the dominant curricular model, ..., with its attendant **deductive teaching strategies**, ... does not reflect what the ... research on learning suggests about how students learn and develop
5. The central lesson that emerged from the study is the imperative of **teaching for professional practice**"

The authors articulate **four principles of curriculum design**:

1. *Provide a professional spine*
2. *Teach key concepts for use and connection*
3. *Integrate identity, knowledge, and skills through approximations to practice*
4. *Place engineering in the world: encourage students to draw connections*

Robin King [6] examined engineering and engineering education in the Australian context and made six recommendations:

1. increase the **public understanding** of engineering ... particularly in schools;
2. **clarify educational outcomes and standards**;
3. **develop best-practice engineering education**;
4. attract a **higher proportion of women** and other under-represented groups;
5. **increase staffing and material resources**; and
6. **promote stronger collaborative links with industry**.

In *A Whole New Engineer*, Goldberg, Somerville et al. [8] trace the innovation that has emerged from Olin College in Boston and the on-going collaboration with the iFoundry at the University of Illinois. They describe the six minds that engineers need to develop: the **analytical** mind, the **design** mind, the **linguistic** mind, the **people** mind, the **body** mind, and the **mindful** mind. However, when we look at curricula, it is the first that gets by far the most attention.

Interestingly, Trevelyan [9] reinforces the need for the *linguistic* mind – his research (and that of others) shows that engineers spend 60% of their time communicating. The *people* mind has a couple of dimensions; engineering is inherently a team activity and it works in the service of humanity. *People* dominate engineering, although this is sometimes not obvious from the curricula.

Goldsmith, Reidsema et al. [12] in *Designing the Future*, report on an industry-academic workshop at the culmination of a project that investigated design-oriented curricula. The **top six trends** affecting engineering practice were identified as: impacts of globalisation, environmental awareness, breadth of knowledge base, engineering systems, rapid changes in technology, and the research/teaching dilemma. The **top six capabilities** were: personal and professional skills and attitudes, communication, design, teamwork, systems thinking, and design of engineering systems.

Despite all these calls for educational innovation, change in traditional curricula, departments and faculties is hard. Ruth Graham [5] interviewed more than 100 change agents from around the world and identified four key attributes of successful change:

1. Change is often initiated by a **significant threat**, e.g. falling retention, recruitment and employability of graduates. Interestingly, such change is often driven by those with **industry experience** and/or new hires.
2. Change needs to be **systematic and connected**, bringing a new wholeness to the curriculum. In the process, it creates a **new brand**, which is easy to sell to others.
3. Change happens at the **Departmental level**, driven by the Departmental Head. Trust in this person's judgement is key, e.g. in future promotion applications that might flow from leadership of change activities.
4. **Change is difficult to maintain**. Successful programs involve most staff, involve systematic evaluation of the program that encourages sustained innovation and reinvention.

Reidsema, Hadgraft et al. [13] identified a structure for systematic change at national level in Australia, involving a partnership between industry, Engineers Australia, the Australian Council of Engineering Deans and the Australasian Association for Engineering Education. Unfortunately, little progress has been made.

Beanland and Hadgraft [7] reviewed the opportunities for transformation of engineering education from a global perspective. Key conclusions include:

1. engineering education must be exciting, relevant and socially responsible, particularly to attract more women
2. the curriculum should be focused on personal transformation based on student-centred learning
3. graduates must become creative, informed, capable and responsible
4. use the extensive literature to inform the transformation of curricula
5. improving curricula will increase completion rates and provide better graduates
6. engineering employers, governments, accrediting authorities and professional engineering associations, must support the universities to achieve transformation
7. changes required are significant – structure, content, delivery modes, objectives, student experiences, staff responsibilities and roles, assessment, etc
8. changes to how universities operate will be necessary – policies, practices, facilities
9. transformation needs to be part of each Faculty's strategic plan

It is also worth reminding ourselves of the context in which engineers work, which is neatly summarised by the Code of Ethics, in this case from Engineers Australia [14].

Demonstrate Integrity, Practise Competently, Exercise Leadership, Promote Sustainability

If these behaviours are to be developed in graduates, then we need a curriculum that is much more complex than teaching applied science and mathematics.

1.1 Summary

It is clear that we need new engineering curricula, ones built around the 'whole engineer' rather than the idea that if an engineer knows enough applied science, the rest is simply application.

Curricula need to expose students early to the complex and challenging problems emerging in the world. Not only will these problems help them to learn design and problem solving, but they will naturally integrate the full set of professional skills: teamwork, communication, ethics, sustainability, etc. – the people-oriented skills that have been shown to be the heart of good engineering.

This is not to argue that mathematics and science are not essential skills for an engineer. However, they need to be seen as analysis tools that serve design in the same way that prototyping does: engineering analysis is simply numerical prototyping. However, design must usually satisfy a complex set of requirements, not all of which are resolvable into neat scientific equations.

2 TYPICAL CURRICULA

When we examine most curricula, they remain reliant on lecture driven subjects covering traditional topics – statics, dynamics, solid mechanics, thermodynamics, fluid mechanics, materials, circuits, control, etc. Many of these subjects last well into third year, giving students in four year programs little time to develop engineering problem solving skills for a world where sustainability considerations are essential – less material and energy use over the product's lifecycle.

For example, an analysis of the civil engineering program at my own university shows the following breakdown:

Table 1. Breakdown of Civil Engineering program at the University of Technology Sydney

Category	Units
General purpose modelling (mathematics and computing)	3
Physical and chemical science	2
Professional skills (communication, design, economics, project management, business)	5
Basics of civil engineering (surveying, construction, materials)	4
Structures	6
Water, hydrology, environment	3
Geotechnics	2
Transport	1
Research and Project	2
Elective	4
Total	32

Of these 32 units, there is a design element in 6 units, accounting for perhaps 50% of each unit, which means that around 10% of the entire program is design. This is not unusual in my experience, having been involved in accreditation panels at a number of universities.

2.1 What are the alternatives?

There are now many universities that have moved to problem and project driven curricula, in whole or in part. Aalborg University in Denmark led the way (since 1974), with 50% of each semester devoted to project-organised problem-based learning (POPBL) [15]. Other variations have been adopted at the University of Queensland in Chemical Engineering [16], Olin College, the University of Illinois's iFoundry [8], the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology (RMIT) [17], Monash University in Civil Engineering [18], Central Queensland University [19], Victoria University in Melbourne, Deakin University [20], and many others around the world.

These curricula implement the recommendation from [4], namely a project-driven spine, typically in each semester of the program, beginning in the first. This project subject is usually 25% or 50% of each semester's work, sometimes expanding to 100% of the final semester of a program.

Two recent innovations in Australia are worth noting: Charles Sturt University (CSU) [21] and Swinburne University [22] are both using 100% project-based curricula supported by industry mentors and online learning. Students are immersed in engineering from day one, effectively providing an on-campus apprenticeship model. In the case of

CSU, students take 3 semesters on-campus before spending 4 x one year work placements, supported by online learning materials and summer schools for upskilling.

Oddly, unlike the medical discipline, engineering has not widely embraced problem/project-based learning, even though engineering is fundamentally a project-driven profession.

The following section takes a deeper look at how program outcomes are represented in accreditation criteria and in some of the research that has examined what it is that engineers do.

3 ENGINEERING OUTCOMES

First of all, what is the nature of engineering? The Define Your Discipline project [23] in Australia conducted more than 20 meetings with more than 200 engineers and asked them one simple question: what *do* graduate engineers do in your company? Participants were encouraged to write as many tasks as they could think of and then to organise them into meaningful clusters.

These meetings revealed *three* sets of interlocking skills: *process or problem-solving skills* such as investigation, modelling, design, management, impact assessment; *technical skills*, which define each engineering discipline, and *generic skills* such as communication, teamwork and collaboration, ethics, innovation, etc.

The *generic* skills are common across every discipline at the university, the *process* skills define engineering, as opposed to other disciplines, and the *technical* skills define the particular discipline of engineering, e.g. distinguishing a civil engineer from a mechanical engineer.

These three sets of skills should come as no surprise since they are easily found in the accreditation guidelines around the world: The International Engineering Alliance (the Washington Accord), ABET, EURACE, Engineers Australia, etc.

However, the three skill sets are rarely articulated in quite this way. Rather we are given a long list of competencies that begin by emphasising an understanding of mathematics and physics. The research shows that *design, investigation and modelling* are the core of engineering practice. Rewriting the accreditation guidelines to put design first could shift our thinking on engineering curricula. The professional skills have also been given greater importance, since this is where engineers spend most of their time, as shown above.

In Table 2, the Engineers Australia competencies have been reorganised, while preserving the original numbering, which demonstrates which elements have been moved to new places. The design criteria have been placed first, since these are what engineers do, supported by the people-oriented skills and the technical skills. This presentation should spark new ideas for curriculum designers beyond ‘let’s start with more mathematics and physics’.

Table 2. Engineers Australia Stage 1 Competencies (reorganised)

Engineering Design Ability	
2.3.	Application of systematic engineering synthesis and design processes.
2.1.	Application of established engineering methods to complex engineering problem solving.
2.2.	Fluent application of engineering techniques, tools and resources.
2.4.	Application of systematic approaches to the conduct and management of engineering projects.

Professional and Personal Attributes

- 3.1. **Ethical** conduct and professional accountability.
- 3.2. Effective oral and written **communication** in professional and lay domains.
- 3.3. **Creative**, innovative and pro-active demeanour.
- 3.4. Professional use and management of **information**.
- 3.5. Orderly **management of self**, and professional conduct.
- 3.6. Effective **team** membership and team leadership.

Knowledge and Skill Base

- 1.1. Comprehensive, theory based understanding of the underpinning **natural and physical sciences**
- 1.2. Conceptual understanding of the **mathematics**, numerical analysis, statistics, and computer and information sciences.
- 1.3. In-depth understanding of **specialist bodies of knowledge** within the engineering discipline.
- 1.4. Discernment of knowledge development and **research** directions within the discipline.
- 1.5. Knowledge of engineering design practice and **contextual factors** impacting the discipline.
- 1.6. Understanding of the scope, principles, norms, accountabilities and bounds of **sustainable engineering practice** in the specific discipline.

This ordering makes a little more sense, by focusing on design and professional practice. However, the wording does not capture the essence of engineering in my opinion. Describing engineering as the ‘application of design processes’ makes it sound like a recipe-following exercise, which design rarely is [24].

The Australian *Threshold Learning Outcomes* for Engineering and ICT [25] also begin with ‘identify the problem’:

Graduates will have the knowledge and skills to:

1. Identify, interpret and analyse *stakeholder needs*, ..., using *systems thinking*, while recognising *ethical implications* of professional practice.
2. Apply *problem solving, design and decision-making methodologies* ... to meet specified *requirements*, including *innovative approaches* ..., while demonstrating *information skills* and *research methods*.
3. Apply *abstraction, mathematics and discipline fundamentals* to analysis, design and operation, ...
4. *Communicate and coordinate* proficiently ..., working as an *effective member* or *leader* of diverse teams, using basic tools and practices of formal *project management*.
5. Manage own time and processes effectively by *prioritising competing demands* to achieve *personal* and *team goals, with regular review* of personal performance ...

These five statements capture what it means to do engineering and are complementary to Engineers Australia’s Stage 1 Competencies listed above.

4 NEW CURRICULA

So, the first step in transforming curricula is rethinking the centrepiece of engineering from technical skills to identifying stakeholder needs and requirements, using design thinking and decision making. Engineering is not merely ‘the application of science’.

The second step is to investigate a range of project-centred curricula from the 100% projects at Swinburne and CSU to 50% (Aalborg University, VU, CQU, Deakin) or even 25% models (UQ, RMIT) as referenced above.

The University of Technology Sydney is currently engaged in remaking engineering curricula in just this way using Studios as the focus of student learning [26]. In fact, a key transformation is not just the curriculum but each student's engagement with it, through a portfolio of career development, beginning in the first semester. Studios focus on student learning through a learning contract. Students become reflective practitioners in their own personal development – EA's point 3.5: *Orderly management of self, and professional conduct*.

However, the real challenges are in shifting academics' thinking about how students learn their discipline, a topic for another paper.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The literature demonstrates that there is an urgent need to redesign engineering curricula, with design and problem solving at the heart of the student experience; this should also be reflected in the way that accreditation guidelines are articulated.

There are many examples from around the world to show how this can be done. However, the evidence is that it is difficult and the main impediment is the academic system, which emphasises technically-focused research as the most important academic activity. A lack of industry experience in the academic workforce is also a serious issue [27].

As the 21st century develops, we see a greater emphasis on innovation and the creation of new enterprises. A recent study showed 40% of my university's students expect or desire to start their own businesses.

So, our engineering curricula need to be sufficiently flexible to develop those three types of engineers identified in the UK Henley Report: the technical specialist, the integrator and the change agent.

We academics need to take up this challenge, to demonstrate our own capacity for change and innovation.

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